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METHOD OF DECOUPLING ANALYSIS TO DETERMINE THE LEVEL OF ECOLOGICALLY ORIENTED DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS

Abstract. The peculiarities of applying the method of decoupling analysis for the implementation of a non-conflict policy in the sphere of natural resource use are considered. The possibilities of decoupling analysis for forecasting and further ecologically oriented development of regions are analyzed. Using the example of several regions, decoupling factors were calculated by resources and environmental impact. It is shown that the obtained result allows to adjust the further economic development taking into account the minimization of the impact on the environment.

Keywords: decoupling analysis, ecologically oriented development, resources, environment, anthropogenic load.

Анотація. Розглянуто особливості застосування методу декаплінг-аналізу для провадження неконфліктної політики у сфері користування природними ресурсами. Проаналізовано можливості декаплінг-аналізу для прогнозування та подальшого еколого-орієнтованого розвитку регіонів. На прикладі декількох областей проведено розрахунок декаплінг-факторів за ресурсами та впливом на довкілля. Показано, що отриманий результат дозволяє корегувати подальший економічний розвиток з урахуванням мінімізації впливу на навколишнє середовище.

Ключові слова: декаплінг-аналіз, еколого-орієнтований розвиток, ресурси, довкілля, антропогенне навантаження.

The Problem Setting. The aggravation of contradictions between the states' desire for economic development and the accompanying increase in the load on the environment requires the search for new scientific and methodical approaches for the implementation of non-conflict policies in the sphere of natural resource use. Scientists, politicians and business representatives understand the irreversibility of the environmental crisis, which today covers all corners of our planet. To resolve ecological and economic contradictions, powerful tools are needed that take into account the peculiarities of the development of various spheres of the economy, help to find the relationship between society, the environment and the social sphere, analyze it and propose ways to solve the problem.

Our state, like many countries of the world, strives to raise the standard of living of its citizens. One way to achieve this is through rapid economic growth. But it, in addition to positive changes associated with the development of the economy, is usually accompanied by stress in the state of the environment. In addition, demographic growth is an additional provoking factor in increasing the need for food products and consumer goods, the production of which requires

the involvement of energy and material resources. If nothing is done in connection with the trend of increasing the burden on the environment, it will inevitably lead to further aggravation of environmental problems. The result of this will be the slowdown of further economic growth and the accumulation of negative consequences, both for the environment and for society in general.

The problem of assessing the relationship between economic development and anthropogenic pressure on the environment needs an immediate solution. It should be aimed at identifying the mutual influence of process components and forecasting their further behavior.

Literature Review. The world community is actively discussing the issue of separating the use of natural resources and the impact on the environment from economic growth. The decoupling concept [1] proposed by an international panel of experts builds on several reports that consider material resources (fossil fuels, minerals, metals and biomass), soil, water, cities and technologies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The main goal of this concept is to achieve a better understanding of how to separate the impact on the environment from economic growth and improvement of human well-being. The methodological basis of the calculations is the concept of “decoupling”.

The concept of decoupling is a powerful tool for assessing the relationship between economic development and anthropogenic pressure on the environment. It allows you to determine the success of the course on sustainable development, the efficiency of management and nature management [4].

Scientists emphasize [5] that precisely due to the formation of ecologically oriented development of individual enterprises or industries, it is possible not only to reduce the negative anthropogenic impact, but also to preserve the efficiency of the economy.

In the paper [6], the authors consider the concept of a new model of the circular economy, which is aimed at achieving the decoupling effect of the negative impact of industry on the environment. The calculation of the decoupling coefficient allows to reveal the inconsistency of the rates of economic growth and environmental pollution.

Aims of the Article – to consider the possibilities of applying decoupling analysis to assess ecologically oriented development of the regions of Ukraine and to show ways of further use of the obtained results.

Presenting main material. The concept of “decoupling” is applied to processes that have a correlational dependence, but at the same time they have the opportunity to move in different directions. The analysis of the obtained results makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented management decisions, to make a forecast regarding further development. The main advantage of using the results of the decoupling calculation is to distinguish between the rates of resource consumption and the growth of the population's well-being. This approach ensures the long-term well-being of the population, regardless of the growing needs. This is achieved through the use of advanced technologies that provide for rational use of nature.

Scientists distinguish two types of decoupling by factors: resource and environmental impact. These views are interrelated and allow us to look at issues of scarcity and resource use from different angles. Thus, the analysis of decoupling by resource factors helps to thoroughly solve problems of shortage of resources, to reduce the rate of their depletion and at the same time to increase the efficiency of their use. Considering the decoupling by factors of influence on the environment, it is possible to determine the ways of a more careful and reasonable attitude towards the environment.

Indicators of economic development, environmental damage or the level of impact on the environment serve as initial data for decoupling analysis. Analysis of the obtained results makes it possible to identify existing problems in the activity, for example, of a separate region or the country as a whole, and to propose programs for further development.

On the example of four regions of Ukraine, namely Cherkasy, Sumy, Rivne, and Mykolaiv, the development of the economic and ecological subsystems of the region was investigated using decoupling factor indicators. The following provisions were used in the analysis: if the value of the decoupling factor is greater than zero and its growth occurs, this indicates a decrease in the load on the environment during economic growth. If the value of the decoupling factor is less than zero and decreases in dynamics, it means that there is an increase in pressure on the environment during economic growth.

The indicator of the gross regional product (GRP), which is traditionally considered a marker of the standard of living, was used to reflect the rates of economic growth. The analysis of decoupling by factors of influence on the environment was performed according to such an ecological indicator as emissions into the atmospheric air from stationary sources. The analysis of resource factors was performed on the volume of water that was taken from natural water bodies. Data for four regions of Ukraine for the period 2017–2021 were used for the calculation [7–8].

The analysis of the initial data showed that during the period under study, there was an increase in GRP for the selected regions. At the same time, the decoupling analysis by environmental impact factors for the Rivne and Sumy regions (Fig.1) shows that the growth of GRP in 2019–2020 is accompanied by an increase in the negative impact on the environmental sphere. Starting from 2020 (Fig. 1), there is an increase in the values of the decoupling factors for all regions that were selected for the calculation, which indicates a gradual decrease in the negative impact on the environment.

At the end of 2021, the decoupling factor can be seen to increase for the four regions, which indicates a decrease in the environmental load with economic growth. In turn, for the Mykolaiv region (Fig. 1), there is a decrease in the decoupling factor in 2019–2020 with a slight increase by 2021. That is, the economic growth of the region is accompanied by increased pressure on the environment.

Figure 1. Decoupling for regions of Ukraine by emissions into atmospheric air by stationary sources: 1 – Mykolaiv region, 2 Cherkasy region, 3 – Sumy region, 4 – Rivne region.

The analysis of decoupling by resource factors (Fig. 2) showed that for the regions selected for the study, in the period 2018–2020, there is a decrease in the decoupling factor, that is, an increase in pressure on the environment.

Figure 2. Decoupling for the regions of Ukraine by the amount of water taken from natural water bodies: 1 – Mykolaiv region, 2 Cherkasy region, 3 – Sumy region, 4 – Rivne region.

Since 2020, the indicators have been increasing, and the greatest growth is observed in the Mykolaiv region. If we compare the calculation results for the regions for both indicators (decoupling by factors of environmental impact and resource factor), it can be seen (Fig. 1–2) that in the Sumy and Rivne regions the nature of the change in decoupling by both factors is almost the same, for Cherkasy and Mykolayiv region – this character is significantly different.

In general, the conducted research showed ecologically oriented development of regions. Their economic growth occurs through the introduction of new technologies that allow reducing resource consumption. Rejecting outdated equipment, carrying out modernization, implementing resource-saving technologies, manufacturers not only reduce the burden on the environment, but also increase the profitability of enterprises due to saving resources, increasing competitiveness in the market. Caring for the environment is highly valued in today's society and helps producers to expand their markets.

Conclusion. The purposeful movement of our state in the direction of sustainable economic development requires enterprises, organizations, that is, everyone who uses various resources and generates emissions and waste, to reduce the level of resource and nature intensity. Such an approach is based on a conscious attitude to the consumption of resources, the continuation of the introduction of new technologies. The successful implementation of the specified movement trajectory requires appropriate state policy. It should be worked out in different directions: stimulation and support of a thrifty attitude to the environment, justified punishment for non-fulfillment of requirements.

References

1. United Nations Environment Programme. (2011). *Decoupling Natural Resource Use and Environmental Impacts from Economic Growth*. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/9816>
2. Naqvi, A., & Zwickl, K. (2017). Fifty shades of green: Revisiting decoupling by economic sectors and air pollutants. *Ecological Economics*, 133, 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.09.017>
3. Guevara, Z., & Domingos, T. (2017). Three-level decoupling of energy use in Portugal 1995–2010. *Energy Policy*, 108, 134–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.05.050>
4. Ivanov, S. V., Vatchenko, O. B., Svystun, K. O., Vatchenko, B. S., & Razumova, H. V. (2020). Decoupling-Analysis of Ukraine's economy regarding its sustainable development. *Science and Innovation*, 16(3), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.15407/scin16.03.003>
5. Шкуренко, О. (2021). Технології розрахунку показника інтегрального декаплінг-фактора як інструмент фундаментальної стратегічної діагностики на основі моделювання біфуркаційних станів соціально-економічних інституцій. *Адаптивне управління: теорія і практика*, 10(20). [https://doi.org/10.33296/2707-0654-10\(20\)-12](https://doi.org/10.33296/2707-0654-10(20)-12)
6. Чуприна, Н. М. (2019). Забезпечення еколого-орієнтованого розвитку хімічних підприємств. *Науковий вісник Полтавського університету економіки і торгівлі*, 3(94), 58–64. <http://doi.org/10.37734/2409-6873-2019-3-6>
7. Державна служба статистики України. *Валовий регіональний продукт*. <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>
8. Міністерство захисту довкілля та природних ресурсів. *Регіональні доповіді про стан навколишнього природного середовища в Україні*. <https://mepr.gov.ua/diyalnist/napryamky/ekologichnyj-monitoring/regionalni-dopovidi-pro-stan-navkolyshnogo-seredovyshha-v-ukrayini/>